

Supplementary table 7 Associations between RF isotypes and smoking, in anti-CCP2-positive and anti-CCP2-negative RA

Subgroup	Exposure		OR (95% CI) ^a	P-value ^b
	CCP2+	Never smoker		
Controls	1280	1589	1.0 (ref)	
RF IgM-	39	86	1.8 (1.2-2.6)	0.3
RF IgM+	339	920	2.2 (1.8-2.5)	
RF IgG-	115	200	1.4 (1.1-1.9)	<0.0001
RF IgG+	263	806	2.4 (2.0-2.8)	
RF IgA-	218	360	1.4 (1.1-1.7)	<0.0001
RF IgA+	160	646	3.1 (2.5-3.8)	
CCP2-				
Controls	1208	1589	1.0 (ref)	
RF IgM-	247	359	1.1 (0.9-1.3)	0.002
RF IgM+	57	142	1.9 (1.4-2.7)	
RF IgG-	258	400	1.2 (1.0-1.4)	0.07
RF IgG+	46	101	1.7 (1.2-2.4)	
RF IgA-	281	435	1.2 (1.0-1.4)	0.01
RF IgA+	23	66	2.2 (1.4-3.6)	

^a Odds ratios (OR) were adjusted for age, gender, residential area, SE and PTPN22.

Significant ORs are shown in bold. ^b P-values indicate differences in ORs between RF isotype-positive and -negative RA subsets.